

This a reference document referred to the CleanSky2 H2020 project [E-TSIN](#): Modular, scalable, multi-functional, high power density power controller for electrical taxi: In this paper, Field Weakening problematical is observed experimentally and finally corrected for high speed operation with an aeronautical PMSM.

As a context, E-TSIN proposal, presented by Indra Sistemas and CEIT jointly, try to answer in the best way the call JTI-CS2-2014-CFP01-SYS-02-02.

The referred call and this associated proposal are framed inside of the packet 4.1.2.4 (Modular power controller for advanced landing system) of the System ITD for the Cleansky2 project. This project will develop a next generation power controller for electric taxi. This controller shall feature increased power density, bidirectional power conversion, modularity, scalability, and multifunctionality to support wide range of aircraft applications. Inside this global project of aircraft electrical moving on ground (e-TAXI), this concrete WP, try to answer the necessity of electrical power converters to:

- Supply new electrical motors inside of the landing gear system (getting energy from electrical sources inside the aircraft)
- Re-charge dedicated batteries inside the aircraft for the landing gear system. This function will help to have additional power available in batteries to be used when necessary, as in acceleration moments. Moreover, the re-charge will be done when aircraft speed on ground is enough or there is a necessity of braking (producing electrical braking over the motors).

Then, proposal solution in this call develops a solution answering both functions and getting a global optimization of the system. This solution is done in accordance with aeronautical standards (environmental constrains), where the participants in this proposal have a vast experience.

This proposal is presented by the consortium INDRA & CEIT that have all competences and skills to develop this project in time and performances, based in its experience in bidirectional and modular power electronic converters and well-known aeronautic standards, rules and process, more when Indra base its business in manufacturing of aeronautic equipment and system, totally verified and qualified.

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Wire Length Impact on Power Electronics Power Density in Aircraft eTAXI Applications

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Abstract—This paper presents an analysis of the output filtering needs of a power converter output port which supplies an electric machine for aeronautical applications. First, the wire connection impact between power electronics and machine is addressed and modelled in order to assess the power quality needs. As more critical operation is defined for a correct power quality requirement using SiC power devices with lower rise time characteristics, filter solutions are proposed and a solution is presented and validated in simulation.

Index Terms—output filter, etaxi

I. INTRODUCTION

eTAXI applications in a More Electric Aircraft context are a present topic of interest for aircraft manufacturers in order to minimize ground fuel consumption and acoustic noise. In general, electric traction of the aircraft is achieved by a PMSM, which is usually located outside the cargo bay, for example in the landing gear or the wheel itself. This means that a certain length will be present between the power electronics and the electric machine. This wire length may lead to perturbations in the motor terminals voltage (overshoot and excessive dv/dt), which may eventually lead to isolation damages in the motor.

While high switching frequency improves the performance of the dcac power stage, the rate of change of voltage (dv/dt) becomes higher and can cause motor insulation failure. This problem can further increase if the motor is located far from the VSI. The long feeding cables can cause damped oscillations and lead to overvoltage at the motor terminals. The overvoltage is due to impedance mismatch between the cable and motor and because of the pulse rise time. Hence, this problem is analysed to determine if a dv/dt filter is necessary or not.

Voltage reflection process is observed in the next figure, where a PWM inverter equivalent circuit sends voltage and current waves to the motor through the wire:

A- Equivalent circuit of a PWM inverter at the sending end of the line

B- Motor terminal treated as an open circuit (large impedance at high frequency)

Current wave is reflected as a negative wave travelling to the left so current at the terminal motor is zero. However, the incident voltage wave is reflected as a positive wave travelling to the left toward the sending end, and voltage at the terminal of the motor doubles.

In a high frequency switched power converter, dv/dt is also finite, so a critical wire length can be calculated in order to foresee the full reflection phenomena.

$$t_t = \frac{l_c}{v} \quad v = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L_c C_c}}$$

l_c cable length;
 L_c cable inductance per unit length;
 C_c capacitance per unit length;
 t_t time for pulse to travel the length of the cable once.

Wire characteristics impact directly on wave propagation speed, and critical length depends on propagation speed and rise time of the pulse, which is directly related to the power device switching rise time.

$$l_{\text{critical}} = \frac{v \times t_{\text{rise}}}{2}$$

Semiconductor Risetime	
	50 ns
	100 ns
	200 ns
	400 ns
	600 ns
	1 us
	2 us
	4 us

IGBT (50 ns to 200 ns)
BJT (400 ns to 600 ns)
GTO (2 us to 4 us)

Rise Time (microseconds)	Critical Lead Length (meters)
2.00	100
1.0	50
0.50	25
0.10	5
0.05	2.5

As SiC power devices present higher dv/dt and lower rise time characteristics, the risk of overvoltage problems in the motor terminals increase.

According to a particular power device, if critical rise time wants to be evaluated, it can be calculated taking into account the voltage reflection coefficient Γ_L , typically 0,9, the cable length, the pulse velocity and the percentage of the maximum peak overshoot admissible (60%).

$$t_{cr} = \frac{3l_{cable}\Gamma_L}{0.66v} = \frac{3\Delta t\Gamma_L}{0.6}$$

Critical frequency is then evaluated:

$$f_{cr} = \frac{1}{2t_{cr}}$$

I. Harness impact modelling

In order to evaluate wire length impact on the motor terminals, a MATLAB/Simulink model is implemented, composed of a simplified step voltage source with definable rise time, a harness model for a particular distance and a motor as a load.

First, with a generic RL load, it can be observed how the wire presence may impact on the motor terminals voltage.

With a simplified model, a single pulse impact may be observed towards the motor terminals.

For particular power quality requirements, it can be observed that motor terminal voltage overpass delimited maximum allowable voltage. Where the blue line is the voltage at the power converter terminal, the yellow is the voltage at the motor terminal and the orange is the allowable limit.

The voltage at the motor terminal is clearly higher than the voltage limit so it can be concluded that a dv/dt filter is needed.

Several dv/dt filters are reported in bibliography, such us:

Filter 1

Filter 2

Filter 3

Filter 4

$$H_1(\omega) = \frac{1 + j\omega RC}{1 - \omega^2 LC + j\omega RC}$$

$$H_3(\omega) = \frac{1 - \omega^2 L_2 C + j\omega RC}{1 - \omega^2 L_1 C + j\omega RC}$$

$$H_2(\omega) = \frac{1 - \omega^2 \frac{R_2}{R_1} LC + j\omega(R_2 C + \frac{L}{R_1})}{1 - \omega^2 LC(1 + \frac{R_2}{R_1}) + j\omega(R_2 C + \frac{L}{R_1})}$$

$$H_4(\omega) = \frac{1 + j\omega R_2 C}{1 - \omega^2 L_1 C + j\omega R_2 C} - \frac{\omega^2 L_2 C(1 - j\frac{L_1}{R_1} \omega)}{(1 - \omega^2 L_1 C + j\omega R_2 C)(1 - j\frac{L_2}{R_1} \omega)}$$

The effect on using each one of them between the converter and the motor can be observed in the next figures:

Filter 1

The impact on the motor terminals voltage is not erased but minimized or controlled according to specific design requirements.

II. Power converter output filter design approach

LC topology

LC filters are the most cost-effective type, but are complicated by the fact that over-voltages can still occur due to the filter resonance. For this reason, these filter are often designed with resonant frequency significantly below (less than ten times) the switching frequency. However, in order to avoid resonance with the load, the filter resonant frequency must be significantly above the output fundamental frequency. This makes the design of the filter difficult for switching frequencies below 10 kHz. The resonance frequency is determined by the product of L and C.

$$f_r = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{LC}}$$

The choice of the individual values of L and C is a remaining degree of freedom. From the view of costs and weight, the capacitor is a much cheaper device. Looking at the inverter current, a big inductance has the advantage that it

limits the current, which the inverter has to deliver for charging capacitors. This current adds to the motor current and is an extra load to the inverter. The capacitor current results from motor voltage, electrical motor frequency and filter capacitance.

$$I_c = \frac{U_N}{\sqrt{3}} 2\pi f_e C$$

RLC topology

There are several low-pass polynomial filter configurations with different shapes of amplitude-vs-frequency responses. The topology shown in the figure was chosen since the series resistor and capacitor combination reduces the power losses across the dumping resistor. A low order filter is desirable from the standpoint of the number of components, filter size, cost and weight.

Its transfer function and the cutoff frequencies are derived as follows

$$H(j\omega) = \frac{1 + j\omega RC}{1 - \omega^2 LC + j\omega RC}$$

$$\omega_c^2 = \frac{2}{LC} + \frac{R^2}{L^2} + \sqrt{\frac{8}{L^2 C^2} + \frac{4R^2}{L^3 C} + \frac{R^4}{L^4}}$$

The first step sets the value of the resistor. The appropriate resistance must be set equal to the characteristic impedance of the cable $Z_0 = \sqrt{L_C/C_C}$. In addition, to achieve an overdamped response the resistance of the filter should follow

$$R \geq 2 \sqrt{\frac{L}{C}}$$

Then the cutoff frequency is selected. This frequency is related to the critical rise time calculated previously.

$$f_c = \frac{1}{2t_{cr}}$$

Once the cutoff frequency and the resistance have been selected the capacitance and inductance of the filter can be calculated by solving the transfer function and the overdamped response condition.

Therefore, the results of the simulation are the following

Finally, a new approach is considered in order to reduce the value of the inductance. A higher cutoff frequency has been chosen. Now it is $f_c = 1/t_{cr}$, although it is not a recommendable practise. The new parameters are calculated and results are obtained for the new filter simulation. It can be seen that an increase on the cutoff frequency will impact the overvoltage level, which increases but does not overpass the maximum allowable.

This way, the impact on the converter weight and volume is minimized. The design could be even optimized decreasing the inductance value until critical requirements are reached.

Critical operation design:

Final step for the analysis and implementation would be the inductor design and correct selection of the capacitor and resistor in order to withstand the current and power on the filter.

The inductor represents the most important component in terms of weight and volume impact of the filter on the power converter. First of all, the size of the core has been determined through the geometrical constant (K_g) method. The geometrical constant is a figure of merit that describes the effective electrical size of magnetic cores. It is related to the geometrical parameters of the core (cross sectional area, window area and mean length per turn) but it can be related to parameters of the inductor such as wire resistivity (ρ), peak winding current (I_{max}), inductance (L), winding resistance (R), winding fill factor (K_u) and maximum operating flux density (B_{max}).

Once the inductor is designed, an estimation of its total weight and volume can be carried out. Finally, in the worst case or most conservative at least, the design of the filter may represent up to the 25% of the total weight of the power converter, which means a decrease of 20% in the power density.

III. CONCLUSION

The impact of the wire length between a power converter and an electric machine has been analyzed. A model which includes a harness electrical model has been used to analyze the negative impact on the motor terminal voltages. As a result, a dv/dt output filter has been added to the power converter and derived optimized voltages have been observed. Two possible filter topologies have been detailed for a possible design. Finally, the impact of the filter on the converter power density has been addressed and optimized, taking the filter design to the design requirements limits.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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